

THE IMPACT OF BIG DATA ON STRATEGIC FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE IN JORDANIAN PUBLIC SHAREHOLDING INDUSTRIAL COMPANIES

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Abstract

This study aimed to demonstrate the impact of big data on the strategic financial performance of Jordanian public shareholding industrial companies, the study relied on the descriptive approach, the analytical approach, and the inferential approach, as they are commensurate with the nature of the study, and the study population consisted of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan, which numbered (54) companies until the end of 2020. The study relied on the theory of the organization, the institution, and the establishment in the interpretation of the study variables. Statistical methods were used, which centered on Pearson's correlation coefficient, variance inflation factor (VIF) and tolerance variance (Tolerance) to test the presence of the phenomenon of multicollinearity. In addition to using Multiple and Stepwise Linear Regression analysis to test the study's hypotheses. The study reached many results, the most important of which is the presence of a strong positive relationship between big data with the strategic financial performance of Jordanian industrial companies. As for the most important recommendations, they crystallized on increasing the awareness of the management of industrial companies on the importance of the big data technology and its role in achieving the strategic goals of the company, especially its financial one, and that is done by reviewing the findings of companies around the world that have committed to applying this technology and exploring its impact on their strategic financial assessment.

Keywords: Big Data: Strategic Financial Performance: Jordanian Public Shareholding Industrial Companies

Classification Codes: L25, L86, M41, C58, C88, D22, D43, G17

1. INTRODUCTION

Big data, in general, represents the raw material for information, as the latter is obtained by performing operations and processing on the data to obtain information of the greatest benefit, and it also assists decision makers in making appropriate and timely decisions, as well as enhancing the company's ability to fully perform its administrative and accounting functions possible (Loudon & Loudon, 2014). Therefore, all companies of all kinds seek to achieve their strategic goals and evaluate their strategic financial performance in the long term, enabling them to reach their basic goals of maximizing profitability, achieving growth, and thus increasing the wealth of owners. These companies have headed towards investing in information to be able to make sound decisions in all Operational, investment and financing activities, and to preserve the available resources and increase the efficiency of their

exploitation, this study worked on showing the impact of big data on the strategic financial performance of the Jordanian public shareholding industrial companies.

2. THE STUDY PROBLEM

The problem of the study revolves around answering the following questions:

1. What is the level of interest of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan in big data?
2. What is the level of interest of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan in the strategic financial performance?
3. Is there an impact of big data with its combined dimensions (size, diversity, speed, accuracy, and variance) on the strategic financial performance of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan?

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study seeks to achieve the following objectives:

1. Identifying the level of interest of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan with big data.
2. Identifying the level of interest of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan in the strategic financial performance.
3. Determining the impact of big data with its combined dimensions (size, diversity, speed, accuracy, and variance) on the strategic financial performance of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan.

Study Model

Figure (1): Study Model

4. STUDY HYPOTHESES:

The study hypotheses revolve around the following:

Main Hypothesis H0: There is no statistically significant impact at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for big data with its combined dimensions (size, diversity, speed, accuracy, and variance) on the strategic financial performance of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan.

The following sub-hypotheses are derived from this hypothesis:

H01: There is no statistically significant impact at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of the size on the strategic financial performance of the public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan.

H02: There is no statistically significant impact at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of the diversity on the strategic financial performance of the public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan.

H03: There is no statistically significant impact at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of the speed on the strategic financial performance of the public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan.

H04: There is no statistically significant impact at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of the accuracy on the strategic financial performance of the public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan.

H05: There is no statistically significant impact at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of the variance on the strategic financial performance of the public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan.

5. DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The delimitations of the study were as follows:

- Spatial delimitations: public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan.
- Humanitarian delimitations: Individuals working at the upper administrative levels (the managers and their deputies) and the middle administrative levels (the directors of departments and heads of departments) specialized in financial matters and information technology in industrial public shareholding companies in Jordan.
- Scientific delimitations: Studying the impact of big data (size, diversity, speed, accuracy, and variance) on strategic financial performance in Jordanian public shareholding industrial companies.

Study limitations

The most prominent limitations of the study were the difficulty of communicating with all Jordanian industrial companies, the lack of response by enough managers and heads of

departments to the questionnaire, in addition to the lack of sufficient studies that dealt with the financial performance from the strategic side.

6. LITERATURE REVIEW

6.1 Big Data – Advanced Technologies:

Information technology has been introduced mainly to improve financial performance and increase business efficiency. Computer developments in information technology came quickly and brought about significant changes in the business environment. The digitization of economic and non-economic data, the Internet, the development of network technologies and cloud computing has caused a rapid increase in the volume of data which helped in the formation of Big Data model, and it is a phenomenon referred to as “Big Data.” As data grows exponentially, new horizons emerge, data usage possibilities grow, and analytics capabilities increase, thus allowing businesses to discover and use new insights from their big data warehouses. Therefore, big data includes techniques and tools for collecting, processing and extracting useful information from big data, and the increase in the size, speed, diversity and value of big data has begun to play an important role in the digital economy (Hajirahimova, & Aliyeva, 2017). Big data is a powerful technology that can generate knowledge and information that managers need to manage the various operations in their companies, for that big data and its applications is used to exploit the power of technology in collecting and processing data to improve decision-making and improve operational processes. From the point of view of (Maroufkhani et al., 2019), exploiting big data revolves around three key benefits of organizations: the data itself, the analysis performed to the data, and the presentation of the results in a way that allows the development of additional value for firms and their consumers.

Big data technology is based on collecting and generating massive amounts of data in order to build and improve the company's ability to generate benefits for it, for such big data technology symbolizes an opportunity for the company to enter a path characterized by benefiting from the volume and speed of data, and this technology can be used to enhance and promote the decision-making process, examine the different uses, and explore the underlying values to optimize the company's ability to generate benefits.

Here (Lukic, 2017) indicates that there is a clear and significant impact of the use of big data in the strategic activities of companies, especially with regard to decision-making processes, which are characterized by speed and accuracy if the company uses big data, in addition to the effect of using this type of data on operational activities, as Operational activities are also subject to the influence of big data technologies, through automation and business process optimization, as well as through the development of organizational capacity to solve problems and eliminating low value-added activities.

6.2 Strategic Financial Performance - An Intellectual Introduction

Measuring and evaluating strategic financial performance is one of the important and sensitive topics for any company, which must be carefully controlled and managed on an ongoing basis (Al-Dahir, 2009, 1). This is for the purpose of benefiting from its outputs in determining the

financial position of the company, discovering and addressing risks and making various financial decisions. Interest in this topic has increased at a time when companies must keep pace with the changes taking place in the business environment, which has forced them to reconsider how they measure and evaluate their performance and their comprehensiveness. For the latter to be achieved, it was necessary to rely on performance measures emanating from the company's vision and strategy, in line with the nature of the surrounding environment, strengthening its competitive position, and ensuring its survival and continuity in the business environment and adapting to its variables and developments. Strategic financial performance: It is the final summary of the company's work and activity, and a reflection of the company's approach to benefiting from its resources and material and human capabilities to achieve its long-term goals. It represents a means to achieve integration between administrative and operational activities and to translate them into the company's strategic vision to achieve its foresight and basic objectives for which it was established for. (Wheelen & Hunger, 2006, 10) Which can be measured through the efficiency of financial performance: which here means the optimal exploitation of the company's resources and capabilities and the generation and maximization of returns at the lowest costs, and through it, the effectiveness of financial performance can be measured: and it is embodied in the value that can be generated from the resources and abilities available to the company, and it reflects the extent of the company's ability to meet customers' needs for products and services.

This applies with the opinion of each of (Gedo and others 2022) who see the strategic financial performance as analyzing the results of the establishments' business to identify the defects and deviations and explain their causes to take the necessary deviations to correct them. In the sense that performance evaluation helps in developing the necessary treatment for deviations before things get complicated because of continuing the wrong implementation. The researchers infer from all the above that the strategic financial performance gives a judgment of pioneering value on the management of the natural, material, and financial resources available to the management of the company seeking institutional excellence at the local and global levels and on the way to respond to satisfy the desires of its various parties.

From the foregoing, researchers believe that the use of big data technology would enhance the information technology of Jordanian industrial companies, by emphasizing a number of basic principles of that technology, which affect the improvement of the strategic success factors of the company, and thus give added value to customers by relying on advanced technology, through which the company's ability to meet their needs and requirements is determined, in addition to enhancing the ability of information technology in the company's internal activities and tasks and its role in achieving integration and coordination between the company and other companies and its positive impact on the company's business strategies, which leads to enhancing its performance and ability in financial aspects.

6.3 Theories related to the study variables:

The importance of accounting was not limited to shareholders, owners, customers, and suppliers, but its importance increased through the need of many groups, as most people practice every day many procedures, events, transactions, and operations of an accounting and

financial nature, and they strive to achieve the general objective of accounting to produce accounting information,

Accounting is also one of the main important sources of information needed by industrial companies and third parties, as it processes large amounts of data through multiple methods and methods, in addition to its relationship with the rest of the company's information systems, within the framework of the accounting information system based on modern technologies such as big data technology.

• **Organization Theory**

The relevance of organizational theory lies in monitoring organizational difficulties, evaluating their causes, and developing intellectual models to solve these problems via the use of various measurement methods corresponding with the nature of the problems' dimensions.

And striving to increase awareness of the movement of organizations and the reasons for their work, so that the leadership in such organizations may profit from the accumulation of knowledge in order to achieve exceptional performance outcomes (Al-Khafaji and Al-Ghalbi, 2009, 19-20).

• **Institution Theory**

This theory seeks to broaden perspectives on the sociology of institutions and describes how they affect society (Huault, 2009, 2).

• **Establishment Theory:**

This approach likewise focused on the market, believing that it reflects the primary indication in economic choices, particularly those concerning production, which Jordanian industrial companies require. (Khader (2012), p. 101)

7. STUDY METHODOLOGY AND TOOLS

7.1 Study Methodology

The study relied on the descriptive approach, the analytical approach, and the inferential approach, so that they fit with the nature of the study. The descriptive approach is based on describing the phenomenon under study through the data collected from the study population and explains its characteristics. The analytical method is based on classifying and analyzing the data collected and revealing the relationship between its various dimensions. As for the inferential approach, its purpose is to draw conclusions and interpret them to reach results that can be generalized and benefited from in all the sections of the study population.

7.2 Study population

The study population consisted of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan, which numbered (54) companies until the end of 2020, distributed over (9) sub-sectors, according to the website of the Amman Stock Exchange (www.ase.com.jo) and the Securities Depository Center (<https://www.sdc.com.jo>). The aim to study Jordanian industrial companies arose from

the fact that they are regarded as one of the most influential sectors in the Jordanian economy, whose existence and continuity are dependent on their ability to achieve financial goals, and they also rely on big data to obtain data and information that reflect the reality of the market and customers, allowing them to make appropriate decisions.

7.3 The study sample

A stratified proportional random sample was selected, which was determined by (47) companies, according to the statistical table (Sekara & Bougie, 2016), which showed that the sample size corresponding to the study population consisting of (54) companies at a confidence level (95%) is (47) company.

7.4 Targeted unit of analysis

Individuals working at the upper administrative levels (the managers and their deputies) and the middle management levels (the directors of departments and heads of departments) concerned with financial matters and information technology in industrial public shareholding companies in Jordan were targeted. To ensure the inclusion of all target groups, (3) questionnaires were distributed in each company electronically, bringing the number of distributed questionnaires to (141).

(123) questionnaires were retrieved electronically, and after reviewing and checking (8) questionnaires were excluded due to the lack of completeness in answering all the paragraphs, so that (115) questionnaires valid for analysis were available, with a recovery rate of (81.6%) of the total distributed questionnaires, which is a statistically acceptable percentage.

7.5 Data collection sources:

Two types of sources were relied upon to collect the necessary data to achieve the objectives of the study, namely:

1. **Secondary sources:** they are represented in books, scientific research, articles, periodicals, theses, and publications related to the subject of the study.
2. **Primary sources:** They are the data collected through the questionnaire that was designed based on the subject of the study, its objectives and questions, and the nature of the data and information to be obtained, after reviewing the literature related to the topics of the study such as books, research, scientific studies and publications that dealt with big data, and strategic financial performance, whether from a theoretical or practical side, through the study tool, and being guided by the questionnaires used in previous studies.

The five-point Likert scale was used to measure the attitudes of the sample members towards agreeing to the paragraphs of the questionnaire, according to the variables of the study model, as follows: (5) to a very high degree, (4) to a high degree, (3) to a medium degree, (2) to a low degree, (1) To a very low degree. The relative importance of the questionnaire's fields and paragraphs was judged as follows:

Table (1): Determining the relative importance of the answers of the sample members

Mean	Less than 2.33	From 2.33 to less than 3.66	From 3.66 to 5.00
relative importance	Low	Intermediate	High

7.6 The statistical methods used

The SPSS program was used to analyze the study data, as the following statistical tools were used:

1. Descriptive statistics measures, which included arithmetic means, standard deviations, frequencies, and percentages.
2. The internal consistency coefficient (Cronbach's alpha) to test the stability of the study tool.
3. Pearson's correlation coefficient, variance inflation factor (VIF) and tolerance variance (Tolerance) to test the existence of the multicollinearity phenomenon.
4. Multiple and Stepwise Linear Regression analysis to test the study hypotheses.

7.7 Stability of the study tool

The study tool stability test aims to measure the accuracy of the study tool (the questionnaire) in terms of the correlation of the paragraphs and consistency among them and their ability to achieve the general purpose to be measured.

It also aims to measure the extent of the tool's ability to give relatively stable results in the event of its repeated use on the same group, under the same conditions and variables. The Cronbach Alpha Test is one of the most common statistical methods used to measure stability, and the reliability is judged based on the value of the Cronbach Alpha Coefficient, which is the amount of the correlation coefficient, that is (0.70) or if it exceeds It then it will be an indication of the stability of the study tool, and the closer the value is to (100%), this would indicate higher degrees of stability for the study tool (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). Table (2) shows the results of the stability test of the study tool.

Table (2): Results of the study instrument stability test

Variable	Dimension number	Dimension	Paragraph number	Cronbach Alpha
Independent variable	1	Size	5	0.806
	2	Diversity	4	0.855
	3	Speed	5	0.822
	4	Accuracy	5	0.849
	5	Variance	6	0.780
	Big Data			25
Dependent variable	Strategic Financial Performance		12	0.919

It is clear from the results of Table (2) that the values of Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the study tool paragraphs ranged between (0.780-0.948), which is greater than the value 0.70, and this indicates that the study tool is characterized with relatively high stability, and therefore the possibility of relying on it to conduct statistical analysis.

7.8 Suitability test of the study model to the statistical methods used

To verify the suitability of the study model for parametric tests and regression analysis, the multiple linear correlation was tested using Pearson's correlation coefficient and variance inflation coefficient, the multiple linear correlation test aims to verify that there is no high linear correlation between the dimensions of the independent variable (two or more dimensions), as the presence of this correlation inflates the value of the coefficient of determination R^2 beyond its actual value (Guajarati, 2004).

Multiple linear correlation test using the Pearson correlation matrix: The correlation matrix indicates that the data is free from the problem of multiple linear correlation, as the values of the correlation coefficient between the different dimensions of the independent variable are less than the value (0.80), otherwise it may indicate a high linear correlation between the independent dimensions (Guajarati, 2004). The results of the Pearson correlation coefficient test for the dimensions of the independent variable are given below.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix of Pearson Correlation Coefficient Values

Dimension	Size	Diversity	Speed	Accuracy	Variance
Size	1				
Diversity	0.637**	1			
Speed	0.729**	0.768**	1		
Accuracy	0.713**	0.644**	0.718**	1	
Variance	0.759**	0.637**	0.742**	0.703**	1
(**) at 0.01 . significance level					

It is clear from the results of Table (3) that the values of the correlation coefficient between the independent dimensions ranged between (0.637-0.768), which is less than the value 0.80, and that the largest value of the correlation coefficient reached (0.768), which is between the variables (diversity) and (speed). This indicates that the data is free from the problem of multiple linear correlation.

Multiple linear correlation test using the variance inflation factor and the Tolerance:

The test of the variance inflation factor aims to provide confirmation of the result of the correlation coefficient test, where the values of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) whose values range between (1-10) and the Tolerance values whose values range between (0.1 –1) indicates that the data is free from the problem of multiple linear correlation. The results of the variance inflation coefficient test and the Tolerance for the dimensions of the independent variable are given below.

Table (4): Variation inflation factor and Tolerance values

Dimension	VIF	Tolerance
Size	2.996	0.334
Diversity	2.582	0.387
Speed	3.714	0.269
Accuracy	2.652	0.381
Variance	3.023	0.331

It is clear from the results of Table (4) that the data is free from the problem of multiple linear correlation, where the values of the variance inflation factor (VIF) ranged between (2.582-3.714), which is greater than the value 1.0 and less than the value 10, and the Tolerance values ranged between (0.269 -0.387) which is greater than the value 0.1 and less than the value 1.

8. DESCRIPTION OF THE DATA AND VARIABLES OF THE STUDY AND TEST HYPOTHESES

8.1 Description of demographic data

To describing the demographic variables of the respondents, descriptive statistics methods were applied, represented by frequencies and percentages; to obtain a general perception of the most prominent personal and functional characteristics and traits of individuals working in the departments and departments concerned with the study in industrial public shareholding companies in Jordan. Below is a description of the demographic data.

Table (5): Description of the demographic data of the study sample members

Variable	Category	Repetitions (N=115)	Percentage
Qualification	Bachelor's	81	70.4
	Master's	23	20.0
	PhD	4	3.5
	Other	7	6.1
Practical experience	less than 5 years	10	8.7
	From 5 to less than 10 years	33	28.7
	From 10 years to less than 15 years	48	41.7
	From 15 years and over	24	20.9
Scientific specialization	Accounting	49	42.6
	Business management	11	9.6
	Banking and Financial Sciences	5	4.3
	IT	41	35.7
	Other	9	7.8
Job title	General Manager / Deputy General Manager	3	2.6
	Department Director	32	27.8
	Department Head	80	69.9

It is clear from Table (5) that most of the sample members hold a first university degree (bachelor's), where their percentage is (70.4%), and the percentage of those holding a (Master's) degree is (20.0%), and this indicates that the study sample members possess Scientific knowledge that enables them to carry out the tasks entrusted to them with sufficient knowledge and scientific know-how. This was confirmed by the percentage of the scientific experience category (from 10 years to less than 15 years), which amounted to (41.7%), as this percentage indicates that the sample members possess sufficient knowledge and practical experience in the tasks and work assigned to them. It was also found that the largest percentage of the sample members are accountants, as their percentage reached (42.6%), and this may be due to the multiplicity of jobs and tasks performed by the accounting department in industrial companies and thus its need for more accountants. It is also clear that the vast majority of the study sample members occupy the position of (department head), as their percentage reached (69.9%), and this corresponds to the distribution of employees according to the administrative hierarchy in modern organizations.

8.2 Description of the study variables

To describing the study variables, descriptive statistics methods were applied, represented in arithmetic means and standard deviations, in addition to rank and relative importance; the aim is to identify the level of interest of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan with big data and strategic financial performance. The following is a description of the variables of the study model.

8.3 Describe the big data variable and its sub-dimensions

The big data variable represents the independent variable in the study, and this variable included (5) sub-dimensions, namely: size, diversity, speed, accuracy, and variance. The following describes the dimensions of big data and the variable.

Table (6): Arithmetic mean, standard deviations, and the relative importance of the dimensions of big data

Number	Dimension	Mean	Standard deviations	Rank	Relative importance
1	Size	4.240	0.572	1	High
2	Diversity	4.117	0.672	2	High
3	Speed	4.009	0.644	4	High
4	Accuracy	3.781	0.841	5	High
5	Variance	4.113	0.589	3	High
Overall Average		4.044	0.579		High

Table (6) shows the high level of interest of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan with big data, where the general average reached (4.044) and with a standard deviation (0.579). All dimensions appeared with high relative importance, as the dimension (size) came in the first place with an arithmetic mean of (4.240) and a standard deviation (0.572), while the

dimension (accuracy) came in the last rank with an arithmetic mean (3.781) and a standard deviation (0.841).

8.4 Description of the strategic financial performance variable

The strategic financial performance variable represents the dependent variable in the study. The following describes the strategic financial performance variable.

Table (7): Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and the relative importance of strategic financial performance

Variable	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Relative importance
Strategic financial performance	4.009	0.603	High

Table (7) shows the high level of interest of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan in the strategic financial performance, where the general average reached (4.009) and with a standard deviation of (0.603).

9. THE RESULTS OF TESTING THE MAIN HYPOTHESIS AND ITS BRANCHES

The hypotheses of the study were formulated to determine the impact of big data with its dimensions collectively and individually on the strategic financial performance in industrial public shareholding companies in Jordan. Size, diversity, speed, accuracy, and variance) on strategic financial performance in public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan. To test this hypothesis, multiple linear regression was used, and the results appeared as shown in Table (8):

Table (8): Results of multiple regression analysis of the main hypothesis

Dependent Variable	Independent Variable	Table of Coefficients			
		B	standard error	T calculated	Sig t* Level of significance
Strategic financial performance	Size	0.366	0.081	4.526	0.000
	Diversity	0.054	0.064	0.841	0.402
	Speed	0.181	0.080	2.265	0.025
	Accuracy	0.159	0.052	3.085	0.003
	Variance	0.282	0.079	3.569	0.001
R. correlation coefficient		0.886			
R². coefficient of determination		0.785			
The calculated F value		79.696			
Sig. F*		0.000			
*Statistically significant at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)					

It is clear from the results of Table (8) that big data has a strong and positive relationship with strategic financial performance, depending on the value of the correlation coefficient R, which amounted to (0.886), and the value of the coefficient of determination R², which amounted to

(0.785). However, (78.5%) of the change in strategic financial performance can be justified through big data, considering the stability of other factors.

As shown by the results of the table, the significance of the model, depending on the calculated F value, which amounted to (79.696) at the significance level (SigF = 0.000), which is less than 0.05, which indicates a positive, statistically significant effect of the big data on the strategic financial performance at the level of significance. ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), and at 5 degrees of freedom.

As for the coefficients table, it showed that the value of B at the dimension (size) amounted to (0.366) and that the value of t at it is (4.526), with a level of significance (Sig = 0.000), which is less than 0.05, which indicates that the effect of this dimension is significant. Accordingly, the researchers reject the first sub-null hypothesis, and accept the alternative that states: "There is a statistically significant impact at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of size on the strategic financial performance of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan."

As for the value of B in the dimension (diversity) it reached (0.054) and its t-value is (0.841), with a significance level (Sig = 0.402), which is greater than 0.05, which indicates that the effect of this dimension is not significant. Accordingly, the researchers accept the second sub-null hypothesis, which states: "There is no statistically significant impact at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of diversity on the strategic financial performance of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan."

The value of B in the dimension (speed) was (0.181) and its t-value was (2.265), with a significance level (Sig = 0.025), which is less than 0.05, which indicates that the effect of this dimension is significant. Accordingly, the researchers reject the third sub-null hypothesis, and accept the alternative that states: "There is a statistically significant impact at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of speed on the strategic financial performance of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan."

Whereas the value of B at the (accuracy) dimension was (0.159) and its t-value is (3.085), with a significance level (Sig = 0.003), which is less than 0.05, which indicates that the effect of this dimension is significant. Based on the foregoing, the researchers reject the fourth sub-null hypothesis, and accept the alternative that states: "There is a statistically significant impact at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of accuracy on the strategic financial performance of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan."

The value of B at the (variance) dimension is (0.282) and its t-value is (3.569), and at the level of significance (Sig = 0.001), which is less than 0.05, which indicates that the effect of this dimension is significant. Based on the foregoing, the researchers reject the fifth sub-null hypothesis, which states: "There is a statistically significant impact at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of the variance on the strategic financial performance of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan."

Based on the above, the researchers reject the main null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis that says:

There is a statistically significant impact at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for big data with its combined dimensions (size, diversity, speed, accuracy, and variance) on the strategic financial performance of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan.

To determine which of the dimensions of big data is more important and influential in the strategic financial performance of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan, a Stepwise Linear Regression test was conducted, and the results of the stepwise regression analysis for the main hypothesis are as follows:

Table (9): Results of the stepwise regression analysis for the first main hypothesis

Model	Big data	coefficient B	Calculated T	Sig T*	R. correlation coefficient	R ² . coefficient of determination	The calculated F value	Sig F*
First	Size	0.862	15.121	0.000	0.818	0.669	228.655	0.000
	Size	0.523	6.783	0.000				
Second	Variance	0.434	5.810	0.000	0.864	0.746	164.341	0.000
	Size	0.406	5.144	0.000				
Third	Variance	0.333	4.400	0.000	0.880	0.775	127.422	0.000
	Accuracy	0.187	3.790	0.000				
	Size	0.361	4.481	0.000				
Fourth	Variance	0.287	3.354	0.001	0.885	0.784	99.709	0.000
	Accuracy	0.153	3.003	0.003				
	Speed	0.149	2.122	0.036				
	Speed	0.149	2.122	0.036				

*Statistically significant at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

It is clear from the results of Table (9) that the dimension (size) is one of the most important and influential dimensions of big data in the strategic financial performance of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan, where it came in first place and explained the amount of (66.9%) of the change in strategic financial performance, The dimension of (variance) came in the second rank, as its addition to the previous dimension led to an increase in the percentage of interpretation to reach (74.6%), and the dimension of (accuracy) came in the third rank, as its addition to the previous two dimensions led to an increase in the percentage of interpretation to reach (77.5%). While the dimension (speed) came in the fourth and last place, as its addition to the previous dimensions led to an increase in the percentage of interpretation to reach (78.4%). The table shows that the effect of all big data dimensions was significant at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), except for the dimension (diversity), which showed a non-significant effect at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

10. RESULTS

1. The correlation of big data with a strong and positive relationship with strategic financial performance, based on the value of the correlation coefficient R, which amounted to (0.886), and the value of the coefficient of determination R², which amounted to (0.785), indicated that (78.5%) of the change in Strategic financial performance can be justified by big data, considering the constancy of other factors.
2. the dimension (size) is one of the most important and influential dimensions of big data in the strategic financial performance of public shareholding industrial companies in Jordan,

where it came in first place and explained the amount of (66.9%) of the change in strategic financial performance, the dimension of (variance) came in the second rank, as its addition to the previous dimension led to an increase in the percentage of interpretation to reach (74.6%), and the dimension of (accuracy) came in the third rank, as its addition to the previous two dimensions led to an increase in the percentage of interpretation to reach (77.5%). While the dimension (speed) came in the fourth and last place, as its addition to the previous dimensions led to an increase in the percentage of interpretation to reach (78.4%). The table shows that the effect of all big data dimensions was significant at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), except for the dimension (diversity), which showed a non-significant effect at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

11. CONCLUSIONS:

1. The high degree of interest in big data and strategic financial performance among Jordanian public shareholding industrial companies.
2. The dimension of (size) is one of the most important dimensions of big data that Jordanian industrial companies place a high value on. This interest was reflected in the company's pursuit of exploring and analyzing large amounts of data once obtained and using it for specialized applications to deal with areas related to large amounts of data.
3. Despite the high level of interest of the Jordanian public shareholding industrial companies in the accuracy of big data and its utilization in finding solutions to the problems created, conducting evaluations for them, determining their sensitivity, and defining them clearly for data users is still below the required level.
4. Mediation of the variation level in big data value among Jordanian public shareholding industrial companies based on the context (topic) associated with it.
5. Jordanian public shareholding industrial companies can enter new markets, increase, and sustain future cash flows, and innovate new activities and businesses to maximize the effectiveness of their scarce resources and capabilities, as well as achieve consistency between the percentage of profits distributed to the company's shareholders and their expectations and aspirations.

12. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Increasing the management of industrial companies' awareness about the importance of big data technology and its role in achieving the company's strategic goals, particularly its financial goals, by reviewing the findings of companies around the world that have committed to using this technology and exploring its impact on their strategic financial assessment.
2. Focusing on providing the necessary infrastructure, competencies, and skills to assist in the application of modern information technology technologies, particularly those related to big data technologies.

3. Adopting strategies, processes, and policies targeted at mitigating the negative impacts of business environment characteristics and variables that have a detrimental impact on companies' strategic financial performance while employing big data technology.
4. Adopting measures to improve Jordanian industrial companies' ability to search and analyze large volumes of data, as well as increasing the skills and expertise of the company's data analysts to deal with this large volume of data using experts and specialists and holding training courses, to raise the level of strategic financial performance.
5. Jordanian industrial businesses' management should undertake a periodic and ongoing examination of the big data they acquire to protect their worth and increase the value of their strategic financial performance on a local and worldwide scale.

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